

The EnBiC2-Lab project is a potential tool in the ongoing battle against climate change. By combining the power of VREs and a comprehensive approach to biodiversity and ecosystem monitoring, this initiative embodies the collaborative efforts required to tackle climate change resilience effectively. As the impacts of climate change continue to unfold, the knowledge and solutions derived from the EnBiC2-Lab project will be invaluable in safeguarding the diversity of life on Earth and building a more resilient future for all living beings.

Link:

[L1] <https://enbic2lab.uma.es/>

Reference:

[1] A. Benítez-Hidalgo et al., “TITAN: A knowledge-based platform for Big Data workflow management”, Knowledge-Based Systems, vol. 232, p. 107489, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2021.107489>

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Exploring the Spectrum of Citizen Engagement through Urban Climate Action

by Christine Liang (Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research) and the CityCLIM Consortium

Cities are a major contributor of greenhouse gases (75% of global CO₂ emissions, according to UNEP [1]) and are highly affected by climate change events such as heat-waves. However, cities also have the resources and power to be catalysts for change and can play a vital role in climate action. The CityCLIM project mobilises citizens with a variety of methods to raise awareness, contribute data and promote climate adaptation solutions.

Citizen science, or the participation of people in scientific processes who are not institutionally linked to that particular field of science, has innumerable social benefits ranging in scale of influence from increasing awareness in participants, to contributing to policies and national reports. Citizen science pushes the boundaries of research by expanding observation networks and databases in scope and availability to a larger extent or variety of spatial and temporal coverage. In the context of urban climate monitoring, citizen science offers

Figure 1: National Geographic Weatherstations being assembled and tested before sending to the pilot cities for use by citizen scientists to collect local climate data.

potential solutions for capturing the high heterogeneity of climate conditions within a city.

CityCLIM is an EU Horizon-funded project that foresees the assimilation of in situ, space-based (e.g. Copernicus) and airborne earth observation (EO) data into a high-resolution (UltraHD) weather model to enhance forecast quality and provide City Climate Services (e.g. Heat Island Simulation and Strategies) to end users. Different simulation model outputs can provide valuable insights to city planners and decision-makers. For example, users from city administrations or the interested public can explore how Land Surface Temperature (LST) in a city changes when urban characteristics are modified (e.g. what if there was more green space instead of a parking lot). The project is driven by four pilot cities addressing diverse cultural and climatic regions in Europe (Luxembourg, Thessaloniki, Valencia, Karlsruhe).

The CityCLIM project is not only unique in terms of its high-resolution model, near-real-time simulations, and urban suit-

Figure 2: MeteoTracker mobile climate sensors for use by citizen scientists on their bicycles. The data is visible to citizens and researchers via a dashboard, instantly visualising the diverse climate conditions of a city in an accessible way.

ability, but also for its use of citizen science as an emerging data source. The project explores the spectrum of citizen science ranging from least to most buy-in: from initial engagement (interactive awareness raising) to crowdsourcing (collecting data from the public) to participatory action (citizens collect data and analyse it). The three citizen engagement tools used in the project are:

1. The Individual Weather Map [L1] is a way that citizens can engage on an individualised level with their local urban climate conditions using an interactive slider to indicate levels of personal temperature preference. Through this, citizens will be able to interact with weather/climate information (e.g. planning their commute to pass through cooler areas), which will motivate and spark interest in climate action.
2. The Historical Weather Data Collection hub allows citizens to submit any personal weather records/observations in CSV format [L2] or through a survey form [L3]. Crowdsourcing historical weather data helps us gain insights into local weather and climate related processes, with a focus on providing knowledge about climate needed for the lives of citizens. It also shows citizens that climate change is already visible and detectable in their local community.
3. A major aspect of the project is collection of in situ climate data (using weather stations – see Figure 1, and mobile sensors for bicycles – see Figure 2), which can be used to validate other sensor systems in the project and ground-truth climate data [L4]. The data will provide opportunities for co-design methodologies for city climate adaptation where citizens and decisions-makers work together. One advantage of co-design is that the participatory role of citizens will more likely lead to policies and adaptation measures that are more relevant to the communities they serve.

The value proposition of CityCLIM is that no other service has explored urban climate using an operational weather model enriched with in situ and EO data while integrating citizen science. There is high potential that lies in the knowledge of local conditions and necessity of working with communities toward climate adaptation strategies. Facilitating citizen knowledge-sharing in decision-making can also foster a greater sense of civic duty and future climate action. Overall, citizen science is a more responsible and inclusive scientific methodology, where full-time and volunteer experts can learn from and with each other on an equal footing. These advantages are what the CityCLIM project aims to yield with its citizen science tools for urban climate monitoring.

Links:

[L1] <https://www.rtl.lu/meteo/cityclim>

[L2] <https://meteologix.com/ua/info/citizenscience>

[L3] <https://survey.hifis.dkfz.de/544485/lang/en/>

[L4] <https://tinyurl.com/ymu7vv25>

Reference:

[1] UNEP, “Cities and climate change,” n.d. [Online].

Available: <https://www.unep.org/explore-topics/resource-efficiency/what-we-do/cities/cities-and-climate-change>.

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Temperature Monitoring of Agricultural Areas in a Secure Data Room

by Thomas Ederer, Martin Ivancsits and Igor Ivkić (FH Burgenland)

Agricultural production is highly dependent on naturally occurring environmental conditions like change of seasons and the weather. Especially in fruit and wine growing, late frosts occurring shortly after the crops have sprouted have the potential to cause massive damage to plants [L1,L2] [1]. In this article we present a cost-efficient temperature monitoring system for detecting and reacting to late frosts to prevent crop failures. The proposed solution includes a data space where Internet of Things (IoT) devices can form a cyber-physical system (CPS) to interact with their nearby environment and securely exchange data. Based on this data, more accurate predictions can be made in the future using machine learning (ML), which will further contribute to minimising economic damage caused by crop failures.

The production of food in agriculture often follows traditional practices, relying on the knowledge passed down from previous generations and on intuition-based decisions. These decisions relate to activities such as sowing, the application of fertilisers, the protection of crops and harvesting. In addition, agriculture is strongly influenced by natural conditions such as location, climate and weather. In sectors such as fruit and wine growing, frosts that occur shortly after crops have started to grow can cause significant damage. As a result, that year's crop is often significantly smaller and of lower quality, leaving the affected farms with some permanent damage. The knock-on effects extend to the market, where such late frosts can lead to scarcer, lower-quality produce and higher prices for consumers. In the most severe cases, some crops may not be available in the local area for an entire season. This requires substitutes to be sourced from distant locations, which increases emissions and has a negative impact on the climate.

Historically, frost damage has been mitigated using a variety of techniques, including water spraying, heaters and fumigation. These methods, while using existing weather systems, are largely manual and often overlook unique local features such as field alignment, wind shelters or nearby water sources. As a result, certain parts of the farm may experience dangerous drops in temperature that can go unnoticed by the system. In anticipation, some farmers employ people to monitor their fields on particularly cold nights, sounding the alarm when temperatures reach critically low levels. Although proactive, this method is expensive, physically demanding and increases the likelihood of human error. In addition, when applying mitigation measures, farmers tend to err on the side of caution and use resources such as water and fuel more liberally than is necessary.

To reduce manual effort in the field and save resources, we present an end-to-end use case of an International Data Space (IDS) [L3] designed for detailed temperature monitoring in agricultural regions [2,3]. The IDS consists of IoT devices

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Climate- Resilient Society

Also in this issue

Research and Innovation:

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JOINT ERCIM ACTIONS

- 4 **Diversity Matters**
by Letizia Jaccheri, NTNU, interviewed by Monica Divitini, as part of the ERCIM HR initiative to create awareness for diversity in the broadest sense.
- 5 **2023 Cor Baayen Early Career Researcher Award for Rianne de Heide**
- 6 **FMICS'23 - 28th International Conference on Formal Methods for Industrial Critical Systems by Maurice ter Beek (CNR-ISTI, Pisa, Italy)**
- 7 **ERCIM "Alain Bensoussan" Fellowship Programme**

SPECIAL THEME

Introduction to the Special Theme

- 8 **Climate-Resilient Society**
by the guest editors Athina Lykos (AIT Austrian Institute of Technology) and Sobah Abbas Peterson (NTNU)

Crisis & disaster management

- 10 **Supporting Landslide Disaster Risk Reduction Using Data-driven Methods**
by Andrea Siposova, Rudolf Mayer (SBA Research), Matthias Schlögl (GeoSphere Austria) and Jasmin Lampert (AIT)
- 11 **Focus Group Facilitates the Use of AI for Natural Disaster Management**
by Monique Kuglitsch and Eri Stern (Fraunhofer Institute for Telecommunications, Heinrich-Hertz-Institut, HHI)
- 13 **A Unifying Technological Ecosystem for Integrated Fire Management and Adaptive Forest Restoration**
by Kemal S. Arsava, Ragni F. Mikalsen and Tian Li (RISE Fire Research, Trondheim)

- 14 **What Role Can 5G Play in the Prevention and Suppression of Climate-Related Natural Disasters?**
by Konstantinos C. Apostolakis, George Margetis and Constantine Stephanidis (FORTH-ICS)

- 16 **Teaching to Survive: A Citizen-centred Disaster Preparedness Project**
by András L. Majdik (SZTAKI), Zoltán Székely (SFC), Anita Keszler, Zsolt László Márkus and Tamás Szirányi (SZTAKI)

Clean air

- 18 **Navigating Carbon Footprints: Insights and Strategies for Sustainable Research Projects**
by Sofia Papadogiannaki, Natalia Liora (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki) and Anastasia Poupkou (Academy of Athens)

20 Improving Urban Air Quality and Climate-resilience in Cities with Inclusive, Policy-relevant Citizen Science

by Pavel Kogut (21c Consultancy), Lieven Raes (Digital Flanders) and Susie McAleer (21c Consultancy)

Energy

21 LoCEL-H2 - Low-cost, Circular, Plug and Play, Off-grid Energy for Remote Locations including Hydrogen

by Athanasia-Maria Tompolidi (Consortium for Battery Innovation, CBI), Jonathan Wilson (Loughborough University) and Hassan A Khan (Lahore University of Management Sciences)

23 Making our Electric Power Grids Sustainable

by Ute Ebert and Jannis Teunissen (CWI)

24 Sustainable Scheduling of Operations: Advancing Self-Consumption through an IoT Data Framework

by Soteris Constantinou (University of Cyprus), Andreas Konstantinidis (Frederick University) and Demetrios Zeinalipour-Yazti (University of Cyprus)

26 Green Mobility Data Spaces

by Anita Graser (AIT Austrian Institute of Technology), Christos Doukeridis (University of Piraeus) and George S. Theodoropoulos (University of Piraeus)

Transferable mitigation pathways

28 KNOWING How to Deal with Climate Change

by Alexandra Millonig and Marianne Bügelmayer-Blaschek (AIT Austrian Institute of Technology)

29 Advancing Climate Change Resilience through Ecosystems and Biodiversity Monitoring and Analysis

by María Luisa Antequera Gómez, Cristóbal Barba González and Ismael Navas Delgado (ITIS Software, University of Málaga)

31 Exploring the Spectrum of Citizen Engagement through Urban Climate Action

by Christine Liang (Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research) and the CityCLIM Consortium

32 Temperature Monitoring of Agricultural Areas in a Secure Data Room

by Thomas Ederer, Martin Ivancsits and Igor Ivkić (FH Burgenland)

34 A Mobile Phone App for Measuring Food Waste in Greek Households

by Prokopis K. Theodoridis, (Hellenic Open University), Theofanis V. Zacharatos and Vasiliki S. Boukouvala (University of Patras)

RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

36 Procurement of Secure AI – A Practical Guide

by Peter Kieseberg, Simon Tjoa (St. Pölten UAS) and Andreas Holzinger (University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna)

38 Luxemverse: Connecting Virtual and Augmented Reality

by Joan Baixauli, Mickael Stefas and Roderick McCall (Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology)

40 Exploring Bias in Public Perception of Artificial Intelligence: A Criticality Map Analysis

by Philipp Brauner, Alexander Hick, Ralf Philipsen and Martina Ziefle (RWTH Aachen University, Germany)

41 INFRASPEC – Automated Inspection of Critical Infrastructure

by Michael Sonntag, René Mayrhofer (Johannes Kepler University Linz) and Stephan Schraml (AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH)

IN BRIEF / ANNOUNCEMENTS

42 CWI and Inria Tackling Societal Challenges

43 Social Robotics, Artificial Intelligence & Multimedia Winter School

43 Dagstuhl Seminars and Perspectives Workshops

NEXT ISSUE

ERCIM News 136, January 2024

Special theme: Large Language Models

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<https://ercim-news.ercim.eu/call>